

RESPONSE PAPER**LAST NAME: ENDALE****FIRST NAME: GULELAT****PROGRAM CODE: PHGH****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA****Edit or delete text to show actual information below:**

The author applied US UK conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics (only keep US or UK)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did did not use Zotero to insert references (remove unneeded text to indicate)

The author did did not use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID) (remove unneeded text)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: (e.g., MSWord 2016 on Windows 8)

QUIZ FOR INTERNATIONAL ACADEMIC WRITING COURSE

1. Which of the following is not true about academic writing?

- Academic writing seeks to provide answer (s) to hypotheses, aiming to communicate ideas based on evidence.
- Academic writing includes research findings or reports on empirical fieldwork, monograph, conference paper, book, or literature reviews.
- Steps in academic writing include researching the topic using creditable academic source.
- None of the above.**¹

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fourth Edition (Bangui: Euclid University, 2021), 7-11.

2. Use of information from the work of another author without acknowledging the source by citation is considered to be plagiarism in all of the following cases except:
- Using the exact words of the author from the source.
 - Paraphrasing the ideas of the author that are associated with a specific source.
 - Using the data the author has compiled through independent investigation.
 - Reproducing a table or chart contained in the author's work.
 - Using the information from the author's work that is a common knowledge.**²
3. The reasons for the citation of sources are:
- To give credit or recognition for authors or sources of information.
 - To reassure readers about the accuracy of your facts.
 - To show readers the research tradition that informs your work.
 - To help readers follow or extend your research.
 - All of the above.**³
4. The following statements are correct about notes-bibliography citation style except:
- The notes-bibliography citation style used widely in the humanities and in some social sciences.
 - Notes-bibliography system employs footnotes or endnotes along within the text and bibliography organized in alphabetical order at the end of the document.

² Ibid., 34.

³ Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Ninth Edition (Chicago and London: University of Chicago Press, 2019), 139-140.

- In the notes-bibliography system, a footnote or endnote generally lists the author, title, and facts of publication.
 - Notes-bibliography style is not appropriate for a difficult argument in a research paper⁴.**
5. The following statements are correct about author-date citation style except:
- The author-date citation style is primarily used in the physical, natural, and social sciences.
 - In author-date citation style, sources are cited directly in the text, in parentheses, by the author's last name, publication date, and page number.
 - In the author-date citation style, a full citation for the source will appear in the reference list.
 - Author-date style is easy for citation of multiple authors, works published by the same author in the same year, and works authored by organizations⁵.**
6. Evaluation of the qualitative problem before conducting the research includes critical evaluation of the following issues:
- Feasibility assessment of access to potential sites and potential research populations.
 - Assessment of availability of sources of information to answer research questions.
 - Assessment of the researcher's knowledge and skills to carry out the research.

⁴ Ibid., 139-140.

⁵ Ibid., 156.

- Assessment of availability of time and resources to collect and analyze data.
- Critical consideration of theoretical implications of pursuing a research problem.
- All of the above.**⁶

7. The key objective of the literature review in qualitative research is:

- To demonstrate your understanding of current leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the research topic or subject of study.
- To enable your reader to understand concepts, theories, and data in your research or study.
- To convince your reader that your research contributes to the current concepts, theories, and evidence.
- To provide a clear and balanced picture of current leading concepts, theories, and data relevant to the research topic or subject of study.**⁷

8. Which of the following qualitative research methodology is an in-depth exploration from multiple perspectives of the richness and complexity of a bounded social phenomenon and is most appropriate to generate understanding and deep insights to inform professional practice, policy development, and community or social action?

- Ethnography.
- Phenomenology.
- Grounded Theory.

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Fourth Edition (Los Angeles: SAGE Publications Inc., 2019), 309-312.

⁷ Ibid., 352.

- Action Research.
- Case study.**⁸

9. Introduction section of qualitative research should state and describe the following except:

- Background and context of the research, including a brief overview of the research topic and what has been researched in the area.
- Clearly state and articulate the main and specific research question or objectives.
- Describe the methodological approach that will be used in the research, including the type of qualitative research design and data collection methods.
- Clearly state the significance of the research, including how the study will contribute to overall understanding of the topic and its implication for practice.
- Discuss any ethical considerations related to the research, including informed consent, confidentiality, and potential risks to participants.
- None of the above.**⁹

10. All of the following are true about WHO style except:

- Numerical referencing is obligatory for the WHO technical report series and the preferred system for WHO publications.
- In WHO information products, diseases and medical terms should follow WHO terminology, which is based on the international nomenclature of diseases.

⁸ Ibid., 159.

⁹ Ibid., 74-75.

- WHO uses North American English rather than British for spelling of disease names and other medical terms.**¹⁰
- WHO uses gender-neutral terms when referring to individuals whose gender is unknown, irrelevant, and non-binary.
- WHO information products should refer age, disability status, racial or cultural background, sex, and sexual orientation only when directly relevant to the subject, preferably by using adjectives rather than nouns.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Road Map from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: SAGE Publications, 2019.

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World Health Organization (WHO). *Style Guide*. Second Edition: World Health Organization Press, 2013.

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.

¹⁰ World Health Organization (WHO), *Style Guide*. Second Edition (World Health Organization, 2013), 12.